

COORDINATING THE PROPER COLLECTION AND PROCESSING OF BLOOD SAMPLES IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF FABRY DISEASE IS AN IMPORTANT FOUNDATION FOR THE SUCCESS OF NEONATAL SCREENING

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Introduction. Neonatal screening, conducted for the purpose of early detection of hereditary disorders and metabolic disorders, is important for the healthy development of adolescents. Proper collection, processing, and transportation of blood samples during screening directly affects the accuracy of the results [1,2,3]. The most effective method is to apply blood from the child's heel directly to the filter paper. This method is a priority for screening. The use of tubes and capillaries containing EDTA or citrate preservatives is not recommended unless blood is taken directly onto filter paper. It is generally accepted that these methods can lead to errors in the results. This holds particular significance in the management of illnesses linked to lysosome buildup, specifically for the prompt and early detection of Fabry disease [4,5].

Materials and methods. Blood-based dry urine tests should be performed by highly qualified medical personnel, and the urine should be stored under appropriate conditions and labeled in a laboratory. Information about the device on which the na'muna will be collected – the last name, first name and patronymic of the child, date and time of birth, gender must be indicated in full and accurately. A number of laboratories are also requesting additional information: about preterm or postpartum labor, the condition of the twins, diet, whether antibiotics were taken, as well as the status of blood transfusion.

Results. Increasing the volume of blood sampling from patients using special methods and their timely implementation in practice leads not only to improved diagnostics, but also to high effectiveness of therapeutic measures. This is especially important in the practice of treating diseases associated with the accumulation of lysosomes, in particular, for the timely diagnosis of Fabry disease at an early stage. In this regard, clinical diagnostics in laboratory practice, ensuring the correct performance of analyses, starting with the

collection of necessary diagnostic information, requires close attention and high qualifications from each medical representative.

Conclusion. Thus, it can be concluded that reliable and accurate results of neonatal screening are ensured by proper blood collection, documentation, and compliance with local medical regulations. This, in turn, can lead to the fact that with a serious approach to procedures, children will be guaranteed health in the future. This is particularly crucial for the prompt diagnosis of Fabry disease at an early stage and for the treatment of disorders linked to lysosome buildup.

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